

A Benchmark Methodology and Evaluation Framework for Edge Accelerators

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Abstract—The demand for edge AI accelerators has begun to grow rapidly over the last five years. The challenge now for developers is choosing the accelerator that best suits their needs, as many of the existing benchmarks are inconsistent and lack realistic performance metrics. This paper proposes an accelerator evaluation framework and benchmarking methodology to fairly and clearly grade accelerators using real-world applications.

Index Terms—benchmarking, edge computing, edge AI, edge accelerators

I. INTRODUCTION

As it continues to grow, the Internet of Things (IoT) collects an overwhelming amount of data [1] from the devices connected within the network. The increase in data quantity has brought challenges, as relational databases and other traditional data systems struggle to process and analyse it. Cloud computing has facilitated centralised data storage, processing and analysis by pooling storage and computational power offered by different vendors [2]. The IoT now has the potential to address latency and security concerns associated with cloud computing by decentralising processing with the edge computing paradigm.

According to Weisong et al. [3], "Edge computing refers to the enabling technologies allowing computation to be performed at the edge of the network, on downstream data on behalf of Cloud services and upstream data on behalf of IoT services". By moving the data processing to the source of the data, edge computing improves network computing by lowering latency, reducing the demand on network bandwidth, expanding spatial distribution and improving fault tolerance [4] compared to a centralised approach.

By looking at the number of papers published on Google Scholar with the key word "edge computing" over the past fifteen years, the development of the paradigm can be plotted, as shown in 1. Shi et al. [5] categorise the development in three stages, the "Technology Preparation Period" up until 2015, the "Rapid Growth Period" from 2015 to 2021, and the "Steady Development Period" commencing in 2021.

Now that edge computing is well established, a new paradigm has emerged in the network computing industry, involving embedding Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) capabilities directly into specialised edge devices [6]. Edge AI facilitates real-time processing of sensor

data, reducing the latency of insights and decision making while also reducing the demand on long term cloud storage of data and increasing fault tolerance [7]. The same analysis performed on papers published on the paradigm indicated that Edge AI has entered the rapid growth period - depicted in Figure 1, which is confirmed by the number of edge accelerators currently available commercially.

Fig. 1. Number of papers related to "Edge Computing" and "Edge AI" on Google Scholar

Edge accelerators are specialized System on Chips (SoCs) designed to perform Neural Network (NN) inference on the edge faster and more efficiently than traditional processors. In June of 2024, Alam et al. [8] performed a survey of Deep Learning (DL) edge accelerators, listing seventy-five accelerators available commercially. With the sheer scale of devices to choose from, a challenge arises for developers when attempting to choose a device that suits their needs. When discussing the performance of NNs, Tera Operations per Second (TOPS) - a measurement of the number of computing operations an AI accelerator can perform in one second at maximum utilisation - has become the default metric to advertise the capabilities of an accelerator [9]. Much like the Millions of Instructions Per Second (MIPS) metric for CPU performance and Millions of Pixels per Second (MPix/s) metric for GPU performance, TOPS are an optimistic metric that will likely never be achieved by the end user [10], [11].

As the edge AI paradigm continues to develop, there is a growing need for more realistic performance metrics to

be used when qualifying accelerators. This paper details the work performed as part of Horizon Europe’s NeuroSoC Project [12], establishing a benchmarking methodology and evaluation framework based on real-world scenarios and utilising real-world performance metrics in qualifying accelerator performance. Section II provides an overview of the NeuroSoC project. Section III details the research undergone when choosing the performance metrics and benchmarking scenarios to include as part of the framework. Section IV describes the benchmarking process, and Section V presents benchmarking results from commercially available accelerators using the NeuroSoC benchmarking methodology.

II. INTRODUCTION TO NEUROSoC

The NeuroSoC consortium is a network of fourteen organisations from across Europe ranging from large enterprises - STMicroelectronics, IBM, and BOSCH - small and medium enterprises - Benkei and Ubotica Technologies - and universities and research centres - Universiteit Leiden, University of Patras, Università di Pavia, Università di Bologna, SCCH, ETH Zurich and Kings College of London.

The consortium has designed a Multi-Processor System-on-Chip (MPSoC) based on Phase Change Memory (PCM) technology with the potential to deliver up to 100-times the computational efficiency of competing commercial accelerators while operating within a low power consumption profile, enabling it to tackle the requirements of a wide set of edge-AI applications. NeuroSoC tightly integrates an Analogue In-Memory Compute Unit (AIMCU), an In Memory Neural Processing Unit (IMNPU), a local digital processing subsystem, and a functionally safe RISC-V microprocessor.

The NeuroSoC accelerator will target a broad range of edge-applications where the platform will offer a compelling advantage. These applications range from space to industrial and even telecommunication applications. The focus of the evaluation framework is to select applications, NN benchmarks and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that demonstrate the benefits of the proposed NeuroSoC hardware approach within these domains. The requirements of the diverse use-cases will drive the specification of circuit and hardware design. In order to compare results with existing industrial solution, a suitable evaluation framework with KPIs and metrics must be defined.

III. RESEARCH

In order to evaluate NeuroSoC a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) must be established along side an evaluation framework to record these KPIs. The following sections present the two key areas of research performed to establish the evaluation framework: an investigation into the current landscape of Edge AI Processors, and an investigation into common applications and NN model architectures. The chosen evaluation framework is then detailed and finally the commercial devices selected for benchmarking within the NeuroSoC project are introduced.

A. Landscape of Edge AI Processors

Edge accelerators are specialized System on Chips (SoCs) designed to perform NN inference on the edge faster and more efficiently than traditional processors. To understand where NeuroSoC will fit in the accelerator marketplace, it is important to survey the landscape of edge accelerators across a performance range from low-power embedded solutions to high performance GPUs. Figure 2 compares the TOPs/W performance published by different manufacturers through a scatter plot. As power budgets increase, the plot shows the range of achievable TOPs. By identifying the TOPs required for specific target applications, Figure 2 informs the performance requirements of NeuroSoC in order for it to be competitive.

Fig. 2. Comparison of manufacturer’s claims of achievable TOPs/W for edge processors

The majority of the edge accelerator architectures can be divided into two primary styles: dataflow and In-Memory Processing (IMP), with dataflow being the most popular.

Dataflow processors are custom-designed for neural network inference and are the most popular architecture for commercial edge accelerators. Dataflow accelerators can be categorised further, the five most popular of which - based on surveys from Alam et al [8] and Pomšár et al. [13] - are Neural Processing Units (NPU), Graphics Processing Units (GPU), Digital Signal Processors (DSP), Tensor Processing Units (TPU), and Visual Processing Units (VPU).

B. Technical Applications

The evaluation framework covers a range of real-world edge AI technical applications to realistically determine the capabilities of an accelerator. The technical applications were chosen first by exploring the use cases of NeuroSoC project partners and then researching the most popular NN architectures being used.

Three main industries were identified based on partner and customer requirements: security, space, and automotive. From these industries, five use cases were derived, along with solution types as shown in Table I. Following this study, and the explosion of Large Language Models (LLMs), there was additional interest in benchmarking a Natural Language

Processing (NLP) model, of which MobileBERT was chosen for its suitability for the NeuroSoC architecture.

TABLE I
PARTNER AND CUSTOMER USE CASES

Application Domain	Use Case	Solution Type
Security	Facial recognition	image classification
Space	Sunspot detection	object detection
	Ship detection	Semantic segmentation
	Fault Detection, Isolation and Recovery (FDIR)	Transformer
Automotive	Multi-task perception	Object detection and classification
NLP	Sentiment analysis	LLM

It is also important to consider the evolution of model architectures. To this end, trends in popularity of different architectures were analysed by examining their presence in public repositories on GitHub. While this does not provide a comprehensive analysis of the popularity of each architecture, it does give an indication of trends in the industry. Presented in Figure 3 is the number of repositories for each architecture, broken up into different programming languages (Python, C++, C, and other). This provides a view of the popularity of each architecture for general ML development - as indicated by Python repositories - and edge applications - as indicated by C++ and C repositories.

Fig. 3. Popularity of DL architectures on GitHub

TABLE II
RECENT UPDATES OF GITHUB REPOSITORIES

Model architecture	Days since last 100 repositories were updated
YOLO variants	1 day ago
UNet	4 days ago
ResNet	8 days ago
VGG	16 days ago
EfficientNet	64 days ago
InceptionV3	143 days ago
FPN	148 days ago
MobileNet-SSD	180 days ago
ResNet-SSD	1994 days ago
Recorded on 11th Nov 2022	

Additionally, by looking at how recently the repositories were updated, the most recent trends in NN architectures can be determined. Table II presents the number of days since the

latest 100 repositories of each model architecture have been updated as of 11th November 2022. In this scenario, the most popular architectures will have been updated more recently.

Some details of the chosen NN architectures and applications are provided in Table III.

TABLE III
SELECTED NN ARCHITECTURES AND APPLICATIONS

Industry	Application	Architecture	Input shape
Space	FDIR	Transformer	1, 100, 1
General	Object classification	ResNet8	1, 3, 32, 32
General	Object classification	ResNet18	1, 3, 32, 32
Space	Ship detection	UNet /	1, 3, 256, 256
		MobileNet	
Security	Facial recognition	MobileFaceNet	1, 3, 112, 112
Space	Sunspot detection	YOLOv5s	1, 3, 320, 320
Space	Sunspot detection	YOLOv8s	1, 3, 320, 320
NLP	Sentiment analysis	MobileBERT	1, 128
			1, 128
Automotive	Multi-task perception	Custom FPN	1, 3, 480, 800

C. Chosen Evaluation Framework

The KPIs for the evaluation framework were selected based on industry standards as well as customer preferences and requirements for design parameters in their solution selection. To establish a meaningful benchmark, general KPIs must be used to relate the performance of accelerators to competing platforms.

1) *Device KPIs*: Typical KPIs for accelerators reported in the literature are the number of TOPs (a measure of processing power), energy consumption in watts (W), and device efficiency per task in TOPs/W. However, as discussed in Section I, TOPs is a somewhat flawed metric for accelerator evaluation. Instead, the processing power of the accelerator will be assessed by calculating the data throughput that can be achieved with unbatched data for each NN chosen.

As this benchmark framework is intended for use in edge computing evaluation, it is also important to consider idle power consumption as a KPI, since this is a key factor in the design of applications with a limited power budget. To assess the power consumption of the device, the Dynamic Inference Power Consumption (DIPC) - the average power consumed during inference, less the idle power consumption - will be measured during inference for each NN.

Initiating an inference run incurs an overhead of loading the NN weights and initialising asynchronous inference setup (if available). This overhead occurs regardless of the number of inference iterations that are to be run. For this reason it is important when performing benchmarking to run inference for a long enough period of time to account for this overhead.

Devices must also be assessed based on the ease of development and deployment of NN architectures to the device, to assess and predict long term adoption of the platform. Further details on this KPI are provided in Section IV-A.

2) *NN KPIs*: The NN KPIs offer insights into a device's performance in real-time inference of the chosen NNs. A device's processing power can be quantified by measuring NN

inference speed and efficiency. The NN throughput, algorithm size, and accuracy when run on the device will be benchmarked.

Throughput is a measurement of the number of inferences an NN can process. The chosen unit of measurement for the NN throughput is Frames Per Second (FPS), which is a measurement of the number of unbatched input tensors processed by a model within a second. The algorithm size of the compiled model, measured in Megabytes (Mb), provides insight on how much an NN architecture can be compressed while still meeting a minimum quality target. Accuracy is the percentage of outcomes that an NN predicts correctly. It is vital that accuracy is documented to ensure that the model continues to perform acceptably when run on the target device.

D. Commercial Device Selection

In order to evaluate the success and usability of the NeuroSoC accelerator, the proposed evaluation framework will be used to benchmark a selection of commercial accelerators to provide a set of comparative metrics. Six commercial accelerators were chosen based on two criteria. The first was to select accelerators that cover a broad range of architectures and performance efficiencies. The second was to select accelerators that address the selected technical applications.

A brief overview of each accelerator selected for this study and the reasons for selecting them is provided in sections III-D1 to III-D5.

1) *Intel Movidius Myriad X*: The Myriad X is a Visual Processing Unit (VPU) with a Neural Compute Engine designed for on-device NNs and computer vision applications [14]. The Myriad X is reported to achieve around 2 TOPS/W and has been deployed in space [15]. The Myriad X was selected for benchmarking as an example of a low-powered VPU and as an example of an accelerator for the space domain.

2) *MemryX MX3*: The MX3 is a stand-alone dataflow accelerator chip utilising at-memory computing that can be cascaded to achieve a reported 5 TOPS/W [16]. Designed with automation, surveillance, agriculture and financial industries in mind, the MX3 was selected for benchmarking as an example of a low-powered accelerator chip and as an example of the at-memory computing paradigm.

3) *Rockchip RK3588*: the RK3588 is an octa-core processor with an ARM CPU and NPU reported as achieving around 1 TOPS/W [17]. Benefiting smart homes, smart cities, industry, facial recognition, driving and security, the RK3588 was selected for benchmarking as an example of an edge NPU.

4) *NVIDIA Jetson Orin family*: The Jetson Orins are a family of edge AI computers designed for generative AI, computer vision, and advanced robotics. There are three Jetson Orin devices that address a range of performance requirements; from the high-performance Jetson AGX Orin featuring a 64 tensor core NVIDIA Ampere GPU that is reported to achieve 5 TOPS/W, to the Jetson Orin Nano with a 32 tensor core Ampere GPU that reportedly achieves 3 TOPS/W [18]. The AGX Orin was selected for benchmarking as an example of a GPU-based edge accelerator and a higher performance

accelerator than the previously selected devices. The Orin Nano was selected for benchmarking as an example of a lower-powered GPU-based edge accelerator.

5) *Qualcomm Snapdragon 8 Gen 2*: The S8G2 is a System on Chip (SoC) featuring a Qualcomm Adreno GPU and an AI engine - a Qualcomm Hexagon DSP - designed for use in high-end mobile devices. Qualcomm has not published details on the processing capability of the S8G2. The S8G2 was selected for benchmarking for its capabilities in running LLMs.

IV. ASSESSMENT PROCESS

As outlined in Section III-C, the framework evaluates the performance of edge accelerators based on five KPIs:

- 1) Ease of use of the toolchain (including whether or not the model could be targeted to the device),
- 2) NN throughput (FPS) when deployed on the device,
- 3) Device DIPC (W),
- 4) Size of the algorithm deployed on the device (Mb),
- 5) NN accuracy when deployed on the device.

This section details the steps taken in order to measure each of these KPIs for an edge accelerator.

A. Network Compilation and Deployment

In order to deploy NNs to an accelerator, the NN must be optimised and compiled to a supported format using device-specific toolchains. Compiled models contain details about how each layer of the NN is mapped to the accelerator hardware.

Once an NN is compiled, it can be deployed to the target device. Deployment consists of running inference with the model on the selected hardware component of the device. Device toolchains may include a deployment tool, or Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) that can be used to create a deployment application. For the purposes of the evaluation framework, a deployment tool must run inference on a set of input tensors, provide the output tensors from the NN, and report the throughput of the NN. Ideally, the deployment tool should also have an option to specify the inference duration in order to fully benchmark the device.

B. Experimental Setup

The experimental setup for benchmarking devices must include methods to record the DIPC of the device and record the NN throughput during inference.

In order to document the DIPC of a device, it was powered by a programmable Power Supply Unit (PSU) that could be polled periodically to retrieve Voltage and Current, and subsequently calculate the power consumption being drawn by the device using the instantaneous power definition (1). The KiPrim DC310S PSU was used within the benchmarking processes of NeuroSoC.

$$Power = Voltage * Current \quad (1)$$

The Myriad X and the MX3 are both coprocessors, where the host PC offloads inference to the accelerator. Input tensors are transferred to the coprocessor during inference and

output tensors are retrieved and transferred back to the host PC. The RK3588, AGX Orin, Orin Nano and S8G2 feature CPUs, and run as stand-alone processors. These devices were benchmarked in headless mode, where no external monitor or peripheral devices were connected. The tensors are stored on the accelerator and inference is initiated through a remote terminal on the host PC. The benchmarking setup for the coprocessors and processors in depicted in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Benchmark experimental setup

C. NN Performance Metrics

The chosen NN performance metric for the NeuroSoC benchmarking framework is accuracy, the percentage of outcomes that the NN predicts correctly. Each NN selected in Section III-C have defined methods of calculating the accuracy of the NN, except for the Transformer and the UNet models. As the UNet model is a semantic segmentation model, the NN performance is determined by comparing the output tensors of the network pixel by pixel to a ground truth label. An example of an acceptable and unacceptable network output from the ship detection application example is provided in Figure 5.

As the transformer model has no method of evaluating the NN accuracy, only the hardware performance metrics are gathered.

(a) Input (b) Ground truth (c) Unacceptable output

Fig. 5. UNet output evaluation example

V. EVALUATION OF COMMERCIAL DEVICES

The accelerator benchmarking methodology was applied within the NeuroSoC project to establish the current capabilities of commercially available accelerators. This section provides additional details on the process taken to benchmark the devices selected in Section III-D.

Details on each device toolchain and carrier board used for benchmarking are listed below.

- 1) **Myriad X**
Compilation - Intel's OpenVINO toolchain
Deployment - Ubotica's CogniSatApp
Carrier board - Ubotica CogniSAT-XE2
- 2) **MX3**
Compilation - MemryX Software Development Kit (SDK)
Deployment - MemryX Python API
Carrier board - MX3 evaluation board
- 3) **RK3588**
Compilation - RKNN Toolkit2 Python API
Deployment - RKNN Toolkit2 lite Python API
Carrier board - OrangePi 5b
- 4) **AGX Orin / Orin Nano**
Compilation - NVIDIA's TensorRT SDK trtexec
Deployment - NVIDIA's TensorRT Python API
Carrier boards - NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin devkit / NVIDIA Jetson Orin Nano devkit
- 5) **S8G2**
Compilation / Deployment - Snapdragon Neural Processing Engine (SNPE)
Carrier board - Snapdragon 8 Gen 2 mobile devkit

In assessing the ease of use of device toolchains, the quality and quantity of the support provided will have the greatest impact. Support comes down to the quantity of documentation available, the quality of documentation available, size of the developer community, direct support provided by device developers, and quantity of example scripts and use-cases provided. The toolchains for each device have been graded on a scale of 1 to 5 in Table IV based on our subjective experience of the support available during the evaluation process.

Device	Toolchain	Grade
Myriad X	OpenVINO	3
MX3	MemryX SDK / MemryX API	5
RK3588	RKNN Toolkit2 / RKNN Toolkit 2 lite	3
AGX Orin / Orin Nano	TensorRT	5
S8G2	SNPE	4

TABLE IV

DEVICE TOOLCHAIN SUPPORT ASSESSMENT

Table V shows the NNs that could be successfully compiled to each device, where a tick '✓' indicates that the NN compiled successfully to the device, and a cross '✗' indicates that the NN did not compile successfully.

It is of note that the custom FPN NN for automotive multi-task perception was not supported on any of the commercial devices benchmarked.

The KPIs for each NN on each device are presented in Table VI. If a device could not support an NN, as indicated in Table V, then it is excluded from the NN results in the table.

TABLE V
NN COMPILATION RESULTS

NN Architecture	Device						
	Myriad X	MX3	RK3588	AGX Orin	Orin Nano	S8G2 GPU	S8G2 DSP
Transformer	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗
ResNet8	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
ResNet18	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
UNet / Mobilenet	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
MobileFaceNet	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
YOLOv5s	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
YOLOv8s	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
MobileBERT	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓
Custom FPN	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗

TABLE VI
BENCHMARKING RESULTS

Model architecture	Model application	Device	Throughput (FPS)	DIPC (W)	Algorithm size (MB)	Accuracy
<i>Idle measurements</i>		Myriad X		1.69		
		MX3		0.78		
		RK3588		2.16		
		AGX Orin		5.79		
		Orin Nano		4.37		
		S8G2		4.12		
Transformer	FDIR	Myriad X	130	0.53	36.8	-
		AGX Orin	2167.2	2.84	0.29	-
		Orin Nano	877.6	1.21	0.11	-
ResNet8	Image classification	Myriad X	237	0.48	0.16	89%
		MX3	8367	4.0	0.17	29%
		RK3588	2871	1.67	0.2	91%
		AGX Orin	2180	2.46	0.51	87%
		Orin Nano	1234	1.63	0.97	89%
		S8G2 GPU	669.18	-0.24	0.3	89%
		S8G2 DSP	924.6	2.2	0.1	88%
ResNet18	Image classification	Myriad X	124	0.78	22.4	95%
		MX3	663	3.45	11.34	34%
		RK3588	283	2.73	22.6	95%
		AGX Orin	581.4	5.51	45.3	94%
		Orin Nano	506.3	3.11	45	95%
		S8G2 GPU	145.32	2.81	44.7	95%
		S8G2 DSP	831.9	3.01	11.2	95%
UNet / Mobilenet	Ship detection	Myriad X	12	1.42	14.6	Acceptable
		MX3	114	3.37	5.86	Unacceptable
		RK3588	50	1.96	10.4	Acceptable
		AGX Orin	95.7	2.86	20.8	Acceptable
		Orin Nano	131.5	1.06	19.3	Acceptable
		S8G2 GPU	118.47	3.71	18.8	Acceptable
		S8G2 DSP	637	1.86	4.8	Acceptable
MobileFaceNet	Facial Verification	Myriad X	36	1.36	6.9	97.8%
		MX3	409	3.51	2.44	97.2%
		RK3588	89	1.46	4.5	96.6%
		AGX Orin	367.8	2.32	10.7	74.6%
		Orin Nano	62.5	1.12	9.4	54.4%
		S8G2 GPU	51.34	2.2	8.3	98.4%
		S8G2 DSP	762	2.52	2.2	98.2%
YOLOv5s	Sunspot detection	Myriad X	20	0.55	3.6	45%
		RK3588	73	1.10	6.6	20%
		AGX Orin	90.3	2.83	9.1	80%
		Orin Nano	81.4	1.28	29.5	80%
		S8G2 GPU	79.2	4.02	28.3	80%
		S8G2 DSP	475.7	3.0	7.2	40%
YOLOv8s	Sunspot detection	Myriad X	12	0.75	22.4	80%
		RK3588	18	1.18	25.6	70%
		AGX Orin	66.2	2.6	47.6	100%
		Orin Nano	7	1.46	46	100%
		S8G2 GPU	49.2	3.8	44.7	95%
		S8G2 DSP	458.7	1.54	11.3	75%
MobileBERT	Sentiment analysis	S8G2 GPU	5.74	3.8	99.8	90.6%
		S8G2 DSP	60.33	2.39	26.6	55.1%

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have presented the edge accelerator evaluation framework and methodology designed and utilised as part of the NeuroSoC project. The framework encompasses requirements of the current market for edge accelerators within the chosen KPIs, model architectures and application use cases that are benchmarked which provides more realistic and useful performance metrics than are currently available for most accelerators.

The merits of the framework and methodology have been demonstrated via market analysis performed within the project, comparing the performance of six commercially available accelerators.

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